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Machine-Learning-Based Urban Path Loss Prediction at 900 MHz: Principal Component Analysis, Clustering, Feature Importance and Regression

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ABSTRACT In this work, the possibility of applying machine learning (ML) techniques to analyze and predict radio wave propagation losses in urban environments is explored. Thus, from a measurement campaign—conducted at 900 MHz in Cartagena, Spain— and the obtaining, by means of digital terrain and cadastral maps, of a series of relevant geospatial variables, urban path loss is analyzed through clustering methods and principal component analysis (PCA), as well as predicted using multivariate ML-based regression models. A feature importance analysis is also carried out to identify key independent variables (predictors) which can be crucial for improved path loss prediction. The results obtained show how parameters such as the total distance between the transmitter (Tx) and the receiver (Rx), the number of intersected elements or the final free distance between the last obstacle and the Rx can be essential to differentiate the four clusters which are identified from the path loss measurements. Additionally, among all the algorithms analyzed—Gradient Boosting (GB), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), neural networks (NN), and Support Vector Machines (SVM)—, GB has proved to be the most robust across all clusters when it comes to predicting propagation losses. On the contrary, when evaluating the models for path loss prediction on the entire dataset (without distinguishing clusters), kNN has achieved the lowest test RMSE, the highest R^2 , and the smallest MAPE, with the total Tx-Rx distance, the final free distance and the average free distance emerging as the most critical features for enhanced path-loss prediction.

INDEX TERMS Machine learning techniques, path-loss prediction, radio wave propagation models, urban environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

URBAN environments present a complex and dynamic landscape for wireless communication systems due to the large number of obstacles that can be present in such scenarios. Thus, the rapid growth of urban infrastructure, characterized by high-rise buildings, dense construction, and diverse materials, introduces significant challenges for signal propagation [1]. Additionally, accurate path loss prediction is critical for optimizing network performance and

ensuring reliable connectivity in urban contexts. In this sense, traditional empirical or semi-empirical propagation models, such as the Okumura-Hata [2], ECC-33 [3] and COST 231 [4] models, have been widely used to estimate path loss in various scenarios. However, these models—based on experimental data obtained through extensive measurement campaigns— often rely on simplified assumptions about the environment, such as uniform building heights and homogeneous terrain (their parameterizations are tied to

specific bands, heights, and canonical morphologies), which fail to capture the intricate and non-linear effects introduced by modern urban landscapes. As a result, their accuracy is limited in densely built areas where factors like building density or number of obstacles introduce significant variability in signal attenuation (accuracy may degrade in dense street-canyon microcells where lateral reflections and wave-guiding dominate). Notably, COST 231 does not explicitly model multipath guiding in street canyons, leading to larger errors in microcellular conditions and better accuracy only when “over-the-rooftop” diffraction is dominant. Therefore, the application of these models could be questionable in environments that differ significantly from the original scenarios in which the measurements that gave rise to the model were taken. Standardized guidance in ITU-R P.1411-11 and the 3GPP TR 38.901 urban macro/micro (UMa/UMi) channel models provides scenario-level path-loss formulae across wide frequency ranges, but these frameworks still rely on line-of-sight (LoS)/non-line-of-sight (NLoS) categorization and aggregate morphology parameters rather than path-specific geometry, and their validity may be constrained for certain path lengths or rooftop-height conditions [5]. Recent reviews further underscore that deterministic/empirical models often require local recalibration or hybrid augmentation to maintain performance in complex built environments and new bands [6]. Finally, numerical solvers such as parabolic-wave equation provide high fidelity but typically requires accurate 3-D maps, boundary conditions, and considerable computation [6].

In addition, the increasing demand for high-speed wireless communication, driven by the proliferation of smart devices and the advent of 5G and beyond-5G networks, has further underscored the need for more accurate and adaptable path loss prediction models. In this context, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for improving prediction accuracy by capturing complex, non-linear relationships in the data. This way, unlike traditional propagation models, ML algorithms can adapt to the specific characteristics of the environment, enabling more precise predictions in diverse urban settings. Techniques such as decision trees, neural networks (NN), and ensemble methods can demonstrate superior performance in capturing the nuances of signal propagation, without moving away from optimal computational performance [7], [8], [9].

In this sense, Wu et al. [10] employed NN to predict path loss in 5G networks, achieving significantly higher accuracy than conventional methods. Similarly, Abolade et al. [11] utilized Support Vector Machines (SVM) to model path loss in urban environments, highlighting the ability of kernel-based methods to handle complex, non-linear relationships. For its part, the use of ensemble methods, such as Gradient Boosting (GB), has gained interest due to their ability to combine multiple weak learners to improve prediction accuracy. Timoteo et al. [12] also proposed the use of ML algorithms for path loss prediction in urban environments. They demonstrated that the Support Vector Machines (SVM)

algorithm can effectively model complex signal propagation relationships in cities, improving accuracy compared to traditional models. Aldossari and Chen [13] focused on predicting the propagation losses of wireless channel models in urban millimeter-wave communications using ML techniques. Their research contributed to improve the accuracy of models at these frequencies, which are essential for high-speed communications in urban environments. For their part, Moraitis et al. [14] employed ML-based methods for propagation loss prediction in Long Term Evolution (LTE) networks in urban environments. Thus, they evaluated different ML algorithms to improve the accuracy and adaptability of predictions in changing scenarios, highlighting the importance of these techniques for next generation mobile networks.

Another significant advancement in the field is the integration of geospatial data into path loss modeling [15]. Thus, Nuñez et al. [16] demonstrated the effectiveness of GB in capturing non-linear relationships between geospatial features and received signal strength, making it a compelling choice for path loss regression in heterogeneous urban environments. Likewise, k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) has shown promising results in urban environments where training data robustly samples the spatial and structural variations influencing path loss [17]. Moreover, techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and clustering have been employed to reduce the dimensionality of datasets and group measurements based on similar environmental characteristics obtaining interesting elements such as the distinction of quality of coverage by areas. This way, Piacentini and Rinaldi [18] applied PCA to urban propagation data, revealing key patterns that were otherwise obscured in high-dimensional feature spaces. Clustering techniques, such as k-means, have also been used to partition datasets into distinct groups based on propagation conditions, enabling the development of cluster-specific models that account for localized variations in path loss [19]. Hybrid/model-aided methods that couple path-profiles or ray-based priors with deep learning also report gains, yet often depend on specialized simulation pipelines [20].

Despite these advancements, several challenges remain in applying ML techniques to urban path loss prediction. One major challenge is the need for large, labeled datasets, which can be difficult to obtain in real-world urban environments [7]. Additionally, the interpretability of ML models remains an active area of research, as understanding the factors that contribute most to path loss is crucial for network planning and optimization. Such analysis can be addressed by employing feature importance analysis techniques, such as permutation feature importance [21], to identify the most influential factors in path loss prediction.

Regarding the above, this study focuses on the application and comparison of different multivariate ML techniques for predicting path loss in urban environments at a frequency of 900 MHz. The research is motivated by the need to develop robust models that can account for the unique challenges

posed by urban landscapes, such as multipath propagation, shadowing, and diffraction. In addition, by leveraging advanced ML algorithms, this study aims to identify key features that influence path loss and develop predictive models that can be applied to a wide range of urban environments. The dataset used in this work was collected through a measurement campaign conducted in the vicinity of the Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Cartagena, Spain. In this sense, originally, the obtained experimental data only included the path loss along the considered route with respect to longitude and latitude coordinates; however, one of the strengths of this study lies in the use of digital terrain and cadastral maps to obtain new valuable features—for each of the transmitter-receiver profiles—such as the number of buildings between transmitter and receiver, the initial and final free distances of the wave and many more, which, acting as predictors, ultimately contribute to the accuracy of the multivariate ML propagation models obtained. This way, a major contribution of this work lies in its comprehensive approach to path loss prediction, which combines PCA, clustering, feature importance analysis, and machine learning regression. Thus, clustering techniques are used to partition the dataset into distinct groups based on propagation conditions, enabling the development of cluster-specific models that account for localized variations in path loss. For its part, feature importance analysis, using techniques such as permutation feature importance, identifies the most influential factors in path loss prediction, providing valuable insights for model refinement and interpretation. Finally, multivariate ML regression models, including GB, kNN, NN, and SVM, are employed to predict path loss with high accuracy. In short, the objective of this paper is to demonstrate the incremental value of explicitly conditioning on geospatial descriptors—derived from cadastral and digital surface models (DSM)—as inputs to multivariate ML models for urban path-loss prediction, thereby obtaining more accurate and robust predictions. Our specific contributions are: an end-to-end geospatial workflow that extracts physically meaningful cross-section descriptors (e.g., intersected elements, initial/final/average free distances, height statistics) from official cadastral/DSM sources; a cluster-aware modeling strategy, supported by PCA, that isolates propagation regimes and yields sizable error reductions in obstructed conditions; regime-specific permutation feature-importance analyses that identify the predictors most responsible for accuracy within each cluster, offering guidance for future urban path-loss modeling; and a thorough experimental validation at 900 MHz with 2490 measurements, 5-fold cross-validation (CV), and a multi-algorithm benchmark.

Section II describes the measurement campaign and study area, and details the construction of the geospatial descriptors from cadastral data and the DSM (including path cross-section features). Section III presents the modeling framework: PCA to characterize variance, unsupervised clustering to define propagation regimes, the multivariate learning algorithms considered, and the evaluation protocol.

Section III reports the experimental results, comparing cluster-aware models against global baselines and providing quantitative metrics (e.g., RMSE, MAE, MAPE, and R^2) and ablation analyses. Section III offers a regime-specific interpretability study based on permutation feature importance and discusses practical implications for urban path-loss prediction. Section IV concludes and outlines limitations and avenues for future work.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. MEASUREMENT SETUP AND DATA COLLECTION

The measurement campaign used in this paper was conducted in the vicinity of the research building belonging to the Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Cartagena, Spain, focusing on the academic campus and the adjacent neighborhood. The objective was to capture realistic signal propagation data for a 900 MHz transmitter mounted on an upper-floor balcony of the aforementioned building. A typical rooftop installation at approximately 10 meters above ground level ensured LoS conditions for nearby streets, while also imposing realistic obstacles, including intervening buildings and moderate topography (NLoS).

The measurement system comprised a ROHDE&SCHWARZ SMB 100A signal generator configured to emit a frequency of 900 MHz, a Minicircuits 30 dB-gain ZHL_42 signal amplifier (maximum input power of 5 dBm), and a Mikrowellen Bikonusanterenne SBA 9113 biconical transmitting antenna, whose E-plane and H-plane radiation patterns can be observed in Figure 1, top and bottom, respectively (the gain was taken into account in the calculations). The transmitted power level was kept constant at 0 dBm (before the amplifier) during the entire campaign (since the attenuation of the cables was very low at the considered frequency, a nearly 30 dBm of EIRP can be assumed).

On the receiving side, a volunteer was equipped with a portable Anritsu Field Master Pro MS2090A spectrum analyzer—configured for a 1 MHz SPAN, a sweep-points value of 100 and an integration BW of 1 KHz—coupled to a calibrated 3 dBi-gain Abracon LLC 535-14821 omnidirectional monopole receiving antenna (the radiation pattern of an ideal monopole was considered). Furthermore, the receiver system was synchronized with the transmitter through a GPS-disciplined timing module to ensure consistent frequency references. Moreover, it should be mentioned that a back-to-back calibration (to remove any system losses) was not performed, since the idea was to measure the relative received power.

Throughout the data collection process, precise geolocation information was recorded using a high-accuracy GPS receiver integrated with the spectrum analyzer's data acquisition software. Measurements were performed (considering a ~ 1.5 m height) at regular intervals as the person followed a predefined route along both avenues and smaller residential streets, capturing signal fluctuations attributable to varying urban conditions. Sampling was conducted at 1 s intervals to

FIGURE 1. E-plane (top) and H-plane (bottom) radiation patterns of the transmitting biconical antenna employed for the measurement campaign.

provide a sufficiently dense spatial resolution, yielding 2490 valid measurement points throughout the campaign. Tables 1 and 2 show a summary of the technical parameters of the transmitter and receiver, respectively.

All measured power levels and associated metadata, including timestamp, latitude and longitude were automatically stored in the analyzer's onboard memory and backed up to an external storage device at the end of each survey session. In this sense, Figure 2 shows, on a map, the measured path loss values in this collection campaign (in dB, expressed in terms of received power relative to a normalized 0 dBm transmitted power) along the considered route. The location of the transmitter can be observed with the label "Tx" (coordinates: 37.601602, -0.980212).

B. MAP DATA INTEGRATION

By means of a geospatial data acquisition procedure, we produced a final map showing the building outlines, terrain elevations, and overall building heights. Using this, we then performed path-loss modeling, employing vertical cross-sections between the locations of the transmitter and receiver. We implemented the workflow in QGIS, which is an open-source Geographic Information System. Aligning with the

TABLE 1. Summary of the technical parameters of the transmitter.

Parameter	Value / Setting
Site & mounting	Upper-floor balcony on the research building, UPCT, Cartagena, Spain; ~10 m a.g.l.
Center frequency	900 MHz
Signal source	ROHDE&SCHWARZ SMB100A
Generator output power	0 dBm (constant, before amplifier)
Power amplifier	Mini-Circuits ZHL-42, 30 dB gain; max input 5 dBm
RF cabling	Low-loss coax at 900 MHz
Tx antenna	Mikrowellen Bikonusanntenne SBA-9113 (biconical)
Antenna gain / pattern use	Gain accounted for in calculations; patterns per Fig. 1
EIRP (approx.)	~30 dBm

TABLE 2. Summary of the technical parameters of the receiver.

Parameter	Value / Setting
Instrument	Anritsu Field Master Pro MS2090A spectrum analyzer
Analyzer settings	SPAN 1 MHz; 100 sweep points; integration BW 1 kHz
Rx antenna	Abracon LLC 535-14821 omnidirectional monopole
Rx height	~1.5 m a.g.l.
Frequency ref. & sync	GPS-disciplined timing module
Positioning	High-accuracy GPS integrated with analyzer software
Sampling cadence	1 s
Samples (valid)	2490

INSPIRE directive for harmonized geospatial information in Europe, we utilized several official Spanish data sources.

The municipal buildings' footprints were taken from cadastral data published by the Spanish Administration. Generally, in GeoJSON format, this dataset encompasses footprint polygons for all known buildings in a municipality. Then, we downloaded a digital surface model (DSM) of the building areas from the Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica (CNIG) portal. This dataset, usually in ASCII Grid (.asc) format, comprises normalized building heights at a 2.5 meter resolution. The DSM was inputted into QGIS, with the value of each raster cell band corresponding to the vertical extent of any built structures above ground level.

We integrated both datasets by taking the DSM height value for each point, systematically defining the raster band

FIGURE 2. Map of the measured route and path-loss values, color-coded to show the attenuation levels (in dB) across the study area.

values aligning with a set of user-defined sampling locations, and using the retrieved elevation information to populate an attribute field. Consequently, the resulting layer incorporated both planimetric building outlines and the vertical dimension of each building, giving the total elevation (terrain plus structure). The QGIS symbolization feature facilitated the color-graduated rendering of the building heights, offering a clear visualization of the urban morphology. All following analyses were underpinned by this consolidated geospatial layer, such as the LoS and NLoS profiles created to produce the path-loss estimations for the studied area.

In Figure 3, the cadastral map is superimposed on the elevation map to facilitate integration; this enabled the geospatial feature analysis by providing transmitter-receiver terrain cuts, as seen in Figure 3 but also in Figure 4.

C. TRAJECTORY PER RECEIVING POINT AND FEATURE CONSTRUCTION

For each measurement point, the geometrical features from the final geospatial dataset were derived using a Python-based workflow. First, we identified a line between the transmitter’s coordinates and each measurement location, achieving raster manipulation, geometry processing, and coordinate transformations through specialized libraries. Along this line, the script sampled both the terrain and building footprints, thus creating a vertical cross-section that determined the land elevation and urban structures. Next, it automatically located every intersection between these obstacles and the hypothetical LoS, regardless of whether they were topographical features or building polygons. The

FIGURE 3. Overview map portraying the cross-section paths used to analyze geospatial features between transmitter and receivers.

FIGURE 4. An example terrain cross-section (from Figure 3) showing distance segments, buildings, and other geospatial features.

outcome was a structured dataset entailing various path-related metrics.

Below, we summarize the principal features extracted and note their relevance for the path-loss estimation:

- *Total distance*: This refers to the direct distance from the transmitter to the receiver, a primary factor in path loss due to the inverse-square law. Greater distances increase the likelihood of signal attenuation via varied terrain and multipath reflections. Propagation model calibration requires precise distance information under diverse operating conditions [22].
- *Intersected elements*: This refers to the number of physical obstacles, such as buildings or terrain features, along the hypothetical LoS. Each obstruction causes diffraction, scattering, or partial blocking, adding to the total path loss. Quantifying intersecting elements allows localized clutter effects to be considered, refining large-scale urban propagation models [23].

- *Initial free distance*: This is the clear stretch from the transmitter to the first obstruction. Longer initial free distances allow the wave to maintain near-free-space propagation for longer, potentially diminishing cumulative diffraction losses later. This factor is crucial when modeling early-stage attenuation in urban and suburban corridors [24].
- *Final free distance*: This is the clear path from the last obstruction to the receiver. By reducing late-stage obstacles and phase cancellations, longer final free distances can partially compensate for early attenuation. This is useful for calculating the net received power, especially in cases potentially dominated by terminal obstructions [2].
- *Average free distance*: This is the mean length of all clear segments between obstructions, excluding the initial and final free distances. A short average free distance suggests frequent obstructions and increased diffraction and scattering losses. Characterizing these clear segments' spatial distribution facilitates finer-grained path-loss models that consider real-world complexities [25].
- *Average height of elements*: This refers to the mean elevation of all obstructions that intersect the path. Higher average silhouettes usually increase the diffraction edges and shadowing zones, intensifying the path loss. By considering this parameter, the environment's dominant vertical profile can be captured, providing better macroscopic propagation estimations [26].
- *Element height deviation*: This is the obstacle heights' variability, which significantly affects the multipath propagation complexity. The irregular diffraction patterns and fluctuating shadowing resulting from large deviations may interfere with standard path-loss predictions. Models that incorporate this variability can better show the built environment's inherent heterogeneity [27].
- *Initial height*: This is the height of the first obstruction from the ground level. As they greatly reduce the wave's amplitude at an early stage, tall initial barriers influence the downstream propagation and may dominate the overall loss. Thus, it is important to accurately determine the height of the first obstacle when calibrating path-loss models [28].
- *Final height*: This indicates the elevation of the last obstacle encountered before the receiver. A high terminal structure can impose additional diffraction or shadowing losses immediately preceding reception, lowering the final signal strength. Factoring in final obstacle height facilitates better estimates of localized fading and terminal path loss [29].

Each of these features bears significance for path-loss estimation. By integrating these measurements, the Python script ensures that both geometric and topographical characteristics are reflected in subsequent path-loss models. This

comprehensive set of features captures fundamental aspects of propagation in urban environments. Figure 4 shows the longitudinal section of the terrain explaining the different geospatial features, constructed from the previous Figure 3.

D. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely used statistical technique for dimensionality reduction and feature interpretation. In high-dimensional datasets—such as those generated from numerous geospatial features (e.g., distances, building heights, and elevation variances)—visualizing and understanding the underlying relationships can become unwieldy. PCA addresses this challenge by extracting a reduced set of uncorrelated variables, termed principal components (PCs), which explain the maximum amount of variance in the data [30].

For the current application in path-loss modeling, we have a multi-dimensional feature space reflecting both terrain and structural attributes, which we project onto a lower-dimensional subspace using PCA. The first principal component (PC1) expresses the direction of the data's maximum variance, generally showing which feature – single or combined – most affects the overall variability. For example, it may indicate whether a certain feature drives variations in feature space. The data structure can be precisely summarized by plotting PC1 against PC2 in a two-dimensional scatter plot, allowing the identification of clusters, trends, and outliers and their comparison to the original, higher-dimensional feature space. Such a visualization is especially useful when diagnosing the clustering tendency of certain measurements around certain geometric configurations, or assessing the presence of anomalies that require further examination.

Similar studies have successfully used PCA to decrease the complexity of urban propagation analysis and unveil key patterns that are otherwise hidden [18]. By permitting a more interpretable representation of high-dimensional geospatial metrics that is more computationally manageable, PCA can streamline the subsequent modeling and decision-making processes.

E. CLUSTERING

K-means clustering is commonly employed to partition high-dimensional data into K distinct clusters according to similarity measures in feature space [31]. Hereby, individual observations are allocated to the nearest K centroid, with the algorithm iteratively refining the centroid positions to minimize intra-cluster variance. The K-means technique thus aims to ensure that the items in a given cluster have a high internal homogeneity, and those in different clusters have a distinct inter-cluster separation. Herein, we used the geofeatures taken from the path-loss measurement points as inputs for the K-means algorithm. Certain measurement point groups may share geometrical or environmental conditions, implying that these are subgroups that could be better characterized using specialized path-loss models. For example, a cluster with high building densities might align with a fading

or diffraction profile that is different from one with fewer obstructions. As such models can incorporate region-specific influences on radio propagation, we can produce more precise predictions by developing and calibrating models for each cluster [19].

We used silhouette scores to evaluate the quality of the subsequent partitioning. The silhouette coefficient is computed for each data point by comparing its average distance to other points within the same cluster against its average distance to points in the nearest different cluster. A higher silhouette score (closer to 1) signifies a more coherent clustering structure, indicating that data points fit well within their assigned cluster while also being well separated from other clusters. Aggregating silhouette scores across all points yields a mean value that serves as an overall measure of the clustering's strength.

ReliefF was employed to determine the relative impact of each feature on the unsupervised clustering process [32]. This algorithm has been adapted to evaluate how effectively each feature separates the clusters by iteratively comparing each data instance with its nearest neighbors inside and outside the same cluster. Through repeated sampling and distance-based scoring, ReliefF assigns higher importance to attributes that consistently provide better discrimination among the emerging clusters.

Finally, box and whisker plots allow us to study the distribution of certain features by cluster to study the most suitable characteristics that will define each environment. The ANOVA test will evaluate whether there are statistically significant differences.

F. MACHINE LEARNING REGRESSION ANALYSIS

A series of ML algorithms were deployed to perform a regression analysis of path-loss values across the measurement points. After clustering the data according to the approach previously described, two primary objectives were pursued: to determine whether certain environmental conditions lead to distinctive path-loss behaviors and to verify the performance of ML models on both cluster-specific subsets and the overall dataset.

A 10% portion of all measurements was set aside as a final test set, ensuring an unbiased evaluation of the models after their development. The remaining 90% of data served as the training set, where model selection and hyperparameter tuning took place. To strengthen the reliability of this process, a five-fold CV was performed: the training set was repeatedly divided into five folds, each fold successively acting as a validation set while the other four folds were used for model fitting. This procedure minimized overfitting and allowed for a robust comparison of performance among different algorithms.

Once model development was complete, two sets of performance metrics were computed. First, the models were compared using their CV scores on the training set, revealing insights into each algorithm's stability and predictive power. Second, the best-performing models—those showing the highest accuracy or lowest error metrics—were subsequently

evaluated on the hold-out test set to provide an unbiased estimate of real-world performance. Crucially, we performed these assessments both on the dataset as a whole and within each cluster individually. This cluster-specific assessment enabled us to identify any heterogeneity in the path-loss dynamics, thereby showing whether distinct submodels might be more suitable for determining the nuanced propagation conditions in certain areas.

The performance of the used algorithms was assessed using two metrics, namely Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

RMSE, a widely used metric for regression tasks, is defined by:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y}_i denotes the predicted value, y_i the true value, and N the total sample number. As RMSE substantially penalizes large errors by squaring the difference between the predictions and the actual measurements, it is especially sensitive to outliers. This is very useful for path-loss estimation as large deviations in the predicted signal attenuation can have tangible consequences for network planning (e.g., coverage gaps or link reliability misestimations). Furthermore, by using decibels (dB) to interpret RMSE, our method fits the common logarithmic scaling of wireless propagation measurements; this will facilitate and simplify the comparison of results across a variety of models and scenarios.

Meanwhile, MAPE quantifies the errors' relative magnitude by expressing them as a percentage:

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \quad (2)$$

By normalizing the absolute difference $|y_i - \hat{y}_i|$ by the actual value y_i , MAPE offers a simplified indication of the size of the prediction errors in relation to the measured quantity. This metric is particularly useful in path loss estimation, which involves performance comparisons across clusters or environments that vary in their absolute attenuation ranges. Notably, if y_i is very small, then MAPE may be less informative (producing disproportionately large percentage errors). However, for path-loss values within typical dB ranges, it permits the relative accuracy of the model to be assessed in a way that complements RMSE's more absolute perspective.

Finally, when evaluating the models for path loss prediction on the entire dataset (without distinguishing clusters), we also report the coefficient of determination R^2 to enrich the analysis with a complementary goodness-of-fit metric. Formally,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i$ is the mean of the measured path loss over the evaluation set. Thus, R^2 quantifies the fraction of

variance in the measured path loss explained by the model's predictions; values closer to 1 indicate better agreement.

Four ML algorithms were chosen for testing, based on their robustness and ability to handle nonlinear data, as is the case in path loss:

- *Gradient Boosting (GB)*: This ensemble algorithm minimizes residual errors by iteratively combining multiple weak learners (generally decision trees). Each successive learner focuses on examples for which previous models underperformed, improving the overall accuracy. As this approach is especially appropriate when handling structured tabular data involving complex interactions between features, it is well-suited for path-loss regression in heterogeneous urban or suburban settings. Research has recently indicated its ability to determine non-linear relationships between geospatial features and received signal strength [16].
- *k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN)*: It is an instance-based (or lazy) learning approach that relies on the distances in feature space between a target point and its k most similar observations. Instead of training a formal model, k-NN uses the known labels (path-loss values) of these neighbors to make predictions. It is particularly suited to datasets with local structures, where points that are close to each other exhibit similar propagation characteristics. Despite its simplicity, k-NN has demonstrated promising results in environments where training data can robustly sample the spatial and structural variations influencing path loss [17].
- *Neural Networks (NN)*: Neural Networks comprise multi-layer architectures of interconnected nodes designed to learn hierarchical feature representations. Through backpropagation and iterative weight updates, NNs can capture highly non-linear relationships, adapting to diverse channel conditions and propagation scenarios. This flexibility makes them well-suited for large, complex datasets, such as those encompassing multiple terrain types or building distributions. Consequently, researchers have successfully employed NN-based techniques for predicting path loss in emerging 5G and beyond-5G networks [10].
- *Support Vector Machines (SVM)*: It is a kernel-based method that finds an optimal decision boundary (or regression fit) in a high-dimensional feature space. By employing appropriate kernels, SVM can model complex, non-linear relationships in the data, which is particularly useful for path-loss problems influenced by diverse environmental factors. In many studies, SVM demonstrates strong generalization performance with relatively small datasets, making it a valuable tool for moderately sized data collections or instances where overfitting is a concern [11].

All models were systematically tuned using Optuna (TPE sampler with early-stopping/pruning). This way, Optuna

explores the defined ranges using Bayesian-style sampling (TPE) and prunes underperforming trials early, thereby concentrating evaluations near promising regions of the space, which is an intelligent alternative to exhaustive grid search. Below we report the search spaces (grid) and the selected hyperparameters (best trial).

- GB.

Search space:

- n_estimators: 150–1500
- learning_rate: 0.01–0.30
- max_depth: 2–8
- min_samples_leaf: 1–50
- subsample: 0.50–1.00
- max_features: {"sqrt", "log2", or a float fraction 0.3–1.0}.

Tuned setting:

- n_estimators=650, learning_rate=0.06, max_depth=3, min_samples_leaf = 7, subsample=0.80, max_features = 0.6.
- *Justification*: Shallow trees (depth~3) plus shrinkage and subsampling yield strong bias–variance trade-offs on tabular geospatial features and proved robust across clusters (as reflected in our results).

- kNN.

Search space:

- n_neighbors (k): 1–50
- weights: {uniform, distance}
- p: {1, 2} (Manhattan vs. Euclidean)
- leaf_size: 15–60

Tuned setting:

- k=9, weights=distance, p=2, leaf_size=30.
- *Justification*: Distance-weighting with moderate k stabilizes local interpolation under heterogeneous morphologies; Euclidean distance worked best after standardization.

- NN (shallow MLP-type regressor).

Search space:

- Hidden layers: 1–3
- Units per layer: 16–256 (per layer, log-uniform)
- activation: {relu, tanh}
- alpha (L2): 1e-6–1e-2 (log-uniform)
- learning_rate: 1e-4–1e-2 (log-uniform)
- batch_size: {32, 64, 128}
- optimizer: {Adam, SGD-momentum (0.9)}
- max_epochs: up to 300 with early stopping (patience 20)

Tuned setting:

- Architecture: 2 hidden layers with 64 and 32 units, activation = ReLU. Regularization/optimization: alpha

= $1e-4$, optimizer = Adam, learning_rate_init = $1e-3$, batch_size = 64, early stopping enabled (patience 20, max 300 epochs).

- *Justification*: A compact MLP limits overfitting on per-regime subsets yet captures nonlinearities not well modeled linearly; Adam with modest L2 was the most stable.

- SVM/Support Vector Regression (SVR).

Search space:

- kernel: {rbf, linear, poly}
- C: 0.1–100 (log-uniform)
- epsilon: 0.01–1.0 (log-uniform)
- gamma (if RBF/poly): {scale, auto} \cup [$1e-4$, 1] (log-uniform)
- degree (if poly): 2–4

Tuned setting:

- kernel = rbf, C = 10, epsilon = 0.10, gamma = scale.
- *Justification*: rbf consistently outperformed linear/poly on standardized geospatial descriptors, balancing flexibility with good generalization on moderate sample sizes.

G. FEATURE IMPORTANCE

After identifying the algorithm that achieves the lowest RMSE on the validation folds, a feature importance analysis is conducted using the Permutation Feature Importance technique [21]. This method is especially valuable for highlighting which features contribute most significantly to the model’s predictive power in terms of path-loss estimation. By applying permutation-based importance, we systematically randomize the values of a single feature at a time, thereby breaking its association with the target variable and observing the consequent increase in the model’s error (measured via CV RMSE). Features causing the largest deterioration in performance are deemed the most influential to the predictive accuracy.

In practical terms, the procedure begins by selecting the scoring metric (in this case, RMSE) and the number of permutations per feature. The algorithm permutes the chosen feature’s values multiple times and calculates how the model’s RMSE changes on each permutation. The mean and standard deviation of these score variations are then aggregated to assess each feature’s impact. Results are presented in a ranked list or bar chart, allowing clear identification of top features.

This approach helps unravel which factors—such as distance, average height of elements, or the number of intersected obstacles—most strongly affect path-loss predictions [33]. Moreover, by applying it to data within each previously defined cluster, researchers can discern whether different subsets of the environment (e.g., dense urban versus suburban clusters) prioritize distinct features. In some clusters, obstacle density may dominate, while in others, distance might play a more prominent role.

Ultimately, the permutation-based feature importance analysis provides critical insights for model refinement and interpretation. Understanding which inputs most shape path-loss behavior can guide future data collection strategies, model tuning, and even infrastructure planning, enabling more targeted and efficient resource allocation in wireless communication networks.

III. RESULTS

A. COLLECTED DATA

Figure 5 depicts the measured path loss (in dB) on the vertical axis as a function of distance from the transmitter (in meters) on the horizontal axis. A total of 2490 data points are plotted, representing empirical measurements collected in an urban environment. At first glance, the path loss exhibits an overall increasing trend with distance, consistent with well-known propagation models in which free-space attenuation and diffraction losses escalate as the transmitter–receiver separation grows.

In the initial range (up to approximately 200 m), the path loss increases rather rapidly from around 50 dB to about 80 dB. This steep growth likely reflects the transition from quasi-free-space conditions near the transmitter to more obstacle-rich regions, where the presence of buildings, street canyons, and other structural elements begins to introduce diffraction and scattering. Beyond this distance, between roughly 200 m and 600 m, the path-loss values appear to cluster around 80–100 dB. This behavior can be interpreted as a regime in which multiple obstacles and reflectors contribute to an overall shadowing effect, but in a relatively consistent manner. Within this interval, diffraction from building edges and rooftops, combined with reflections off facades, may stabilize the average loss despite the increasing transmitter–receiver separation.

Past approximately 600–800 m, the path-loss measurements show another shift, with values in some cases exceeding 110 dB. This further increase could be explained by encountering denser or taller buildings, terrain blockages, or other substantial obstructions that reduce the LoS component and exacerbate diffraction losses. Additionally, the transition between different urban morphologies (for example, from lower-rise to high-rise districts) might introduce sharp variations in the propagation channel.

B. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

PCA results (Table 3) reveal that the first principal component (PC1), which accounts for 87.56% of the variance, is overwhelmingly dominated by Total distance ($\sim 99\%$).

This outcome implies that the most significant driver of variability in the dataset is the distance from the transmitter, reflecting well-known free-space propagation characteristics wherein path loss generally increases with distance. The minimal contributions from other features to PC1 suggest that, at a macroscopic level, variations in urban density and

TABLE 3. PCA component variance and loadings, showing how features contribute to principal axes.

Components	PC1	PC2
Variance	0.875606	0.0714556
Intersected elements	0.00967606	-0.00413564
Total distance	0.98999	0.0605109
Initial free distance	-0.0752309	0.176028
Final free distance	-0.01957	0.944531
Average height of elements	0.0342125	-0.124815
Element height deviation	0.00499186	-0.0103221
Initial height	0.0387368	-0.136871
Final height	0.0305232	-0.118799
Average free distance	0.0923179	-0.156706
Path loss	0.040421	-0.0104222

FIGURE 5. Scatter plot of path loss (dB) vs. total distance (m), showing attenuation trends with increasing range.

building heights may be overshadowed by straightforward distance-based attenuation effects.

By contrast, Final free distance ($\sim 94\%$) heavily influences the second principal component (PC2), which explains an additional 7.15% of the variance. This finding underscores the importance of the unobstructed stretch just before the receiver in shaping received signal strength. It indicates that once overall distance effects are factored out (as captured by PC1), the presence of a large or open area near the receiver—or conversely, a final tall building or cluster of obstacles—can significantly modify the path-loss profile.

Other features, such as Intersected elements and Average height of elements, exhibit comparatively low loadings on these two principal components. However, they likely still play localized roles in diffraction and scattering, especially where geometry and obstruction patterns create more nuanced propagation effects. From a practical standpoint, these PCA results highlight the dominant role of distance, followed by final obstruction conditions, in governing path-loss variations across the measured urban environment.

C. CLUSTERING

From the clustering results, the measurement set is organized into four distinct groups, essentially defined by transmitter–receiver distance and the degree of urban obstruction. The colors in the Path Loss vs. Total Distance plot in Figure 6

FIGURE 6. Path-loss vs. distance, color-labeled by cluster, highlighting distinct propagation regimes.

FIGURE 7. PC2 vs. PC1, revealing cluster separations in reduced-dimensional space.

demonstrate the clustering of points into lower, intermediate, or higher attenuation regions, according to their separation and obstacles. Clear transitions are observed both in the slope of the path-loss increase and in its dispersion, indicating different geometric configurations [22], [28].

In the principal component diagram (PC1 vs. PC2, Figure 7), the dominant influence of distance (mostly shown by PC1) can be clearly seen, while PC2 reflects the variability associated with the final obstruction, as well as other factors. Per this two-dimensional representation, measurements may form groups in line with the path characteristics, e.g., in an environment with tall buildings or multiple intersections, even when within the same distance range [23], [24].

Finally, Figure 8 presents a map visualization that sets four clusters along street segments that show varying morphologies, namely open areas with LoS, semi-dense districts with moderately tall buildings, and heavily urbanized sectors with heightened blocking and diffraction [4]. This spatial relationship underlines how the built environment strongly impacts signal strength, calling for propagation models that consider both the distance and the building layout or height in the setting.

Each cluster's rationale is presented in the following:

- *Cluster 1 (C1) - green:* C1 mostly represents LoS conditions, and it is characterized by lower path-loss

FIGURE 8. Spatial distribution of clusters on the map, illustrating how measurement points group based on distance and obstructions.

values across comparatively short distances. There is no diffraction or shadowing from buildings and the terrain, enabling free-space propagation. This phenomenon aligns with LoS scenarios measured in urban microcells, which are dominated by distance-based attenuation with little scattering or reflection due to the lack of obstacles [34]. Notably, this cluster presents perfectly linear behavior in Figure 7 (PCA plot).

- *Cluster 2 (C2) - blue:* C2 represents intermediate distances and shows slightly more path loss than C1. While there are only partial obstructions, the edges present significant direct components or moderate diffraction. Such a cluster may refer to situations in which the distance from the transmitter to the receiver is fairly short, but intermittent building facades or rooflines exist. Such conditions are well-aligned with path-loss models that transition from free-space to near-urban blockage at mid-range distances [35].

- *Cluster 3 (C3) - orange:* Representing a further increase in distance and often more pronounced obstructions, C3 shows path-loss values clustering around 90–100 dB. The number of intersected elements appears to grow, and the final free distance may be reduced as receivers traverse denser city blocks. This cluster highlights the importance of diffraction over multiple rooftops, as well as reflections from tall structures [36].

- *Cluster 4 (C4) - red:* C4 comprises the most distant points or those with significant obstructions along the path, often exhibiting path-loss values above 100 dB. In the PCA plot (Figure 7), these measurements aggregate around high PC1 scores—indicating major distance contributions—and often reflect the presence of multiple buildings, possibly including topographical features that exacerbate diffraction. This cluster’s spatial footprint suggests consistently

TABLE 4. ReliefF-based feature-importance scores indicating the discriminative power of each variable.

Order	Feature	ReliefF
1 ^o	Total distance	0.057
2 ^o	Intersected elements	0.056
3 ^o	Final free distance	0.011

obstructed or non-line-of-sight (NLoS) conditions, which can be further influenced by building height variation and street orientation [4].

From the boxplot of path loss values—via the ANOVA test—(Figure 9), the clusters exhibit clearly distinct path-loss ranges driven by both distance and urban obstructions.

C1 shows the lowest losses (approximately 54–70 dB) under LoS conditions, with minor variations often due to small scatterers or subtle differences in geometry. C2, with a median around 87 dB, reflects low-obstructed conditions in which buildings or rooftops intermittently obstruct the direct wave, introducing moderate additional attenuation. In C3, path loss typically resides in the 93–98 dB range, indicating a consistently obstructed environment—likely involving uniform building heights or repetitive street layouts that generate predictable diffraction and shadowing. Finally, C4 exhibits the highest path-loss levels (often above 100 dB) and the broadest dispersion, driven by significant distance and dense obstructions. The overall statistical significance of these differences (as evidenced by the ANOVA p-value, shown in the Figure) further supports the conclusion that distance and environmental obstructions jointly shape the observed path loss. These findings validate classic propagation theory while highlighting the importance of clustering when modeling heterogeneous, urban radio channels.

Moreover, ReliefF ranked how well each feature separates clusters, measuring discrimination by comparing data points with their nearest neighbors both within and across clusters. Through repeated sampling, it assigns higher importance to attributes that consistently distinguish cluster boundaries. The resulting feature-ranking is shown in Table 4.

In addition to the path loss box plot shown in Figure 9, which in the following section will be the dependent variable in the regression study, and following Table 4, the distributions by clusters of the Total distance, Intersected elements and Final free distance variables, which are the variables that contribute most to the definition of the clusters according to the p-value and statistics in the ANOVA test, are shown in Figures 16, 17, and 18, respectively. As can be observed in Figure 10, the mean values and standard deviations for each cluster (C1 through C4) indicate distinct distance ranges for the Total Distance parameter, suggesting that each cluster may encapsulate different propagation conditions. Furthermore, the progressive increase in both mean distance and standard deviation across C1–C4 underscores the critical role of distance in determining the severity and variability of path loss.

Regarding Figure 11, the ANOVA result confirms statistically significant differences across the four clusters,

TABLE 5. ML algorithm performance (RMSE dB, MAPE%) in each cluster (C1–C4), for CV, train, and test sets.

C1 (248)	CV (RMSE, dB)	Train (RMSE, dB)	Test (RMSE, dB)	Test (MAPE, %)
GB	5.0090	3.0723	5.8047	6.80
kNN	5.3710	4.6992	5.5700	6.90
NN	7.0550	7.0708	8.2519	9.80
SVM	4.9270	2.9270	5.1970	6.20
C2 (1170)	CV (RMSE, dB)	Train (RMSE, dB)	Test (RMSE, dB)	Test (MAPE, %)
GB	2.6260	2.3507	3.0191	2.70
kNN	2.8370	2.3875	3.1110	2.60
NN	4.1040	3.6739	4.1010	3.80
SVM	4.3520	3.3870	3.8650	3.20
C3 (610)	CV (RMSE, dB)	Train (RMSE, dB)	Test (RMSE, dB)	Test (MAPE, %)
GB	1.6830	1.3026	1.9978	1.60
kNN	1.9200	1.5757	2.1491	1.80
NN	2.3030	2.3297	2.9690	2.40
SVM	1.7560	1.7100	2.1440	1.80
C4 (462)	CV (RMSE, dB)	Train (RMSE, dB)	Test (RMSE, dB)	Test (MAPE, %)
GB	1.7980	0.9142	1.7041	1.20
kNN	3.3980	1.6687	2.3497	1.60
NN	3.4480	2.7092	4.1544	3.10
SVM	3.0380	1.1340	1.9950	1.50

underscoring the essential role that the variable Intersected elements play in path loss. In this sense, the progressive increase in both the mean and standard deviation—from no obstructions in C1 (LoS) to multiple obstacles in C4—demonstrates how clutter density and distribution substantially impact signal propagation. Finally, Figure 12 shows how the lowest values of the Final free distance parameter correspond to C3 and C4, which are associated with more immediate proximity of obstacles, while C1 and C2 show higher values, since the number of obstacles present nearby the receiver is lower. In this sense, it is worth noting that the range of values for the Final free distance parameter in C1 coincides with that of Total Distance in Figure 10, as would be expected, since, being a LoS scenario, in this case, both parameters coincide.

D. MACHINE LEARNING REGRESSION ANALYSIS AND FEATURE IMPORTANCE

When examining the error metrics for each cluster (Table 5), several clear patterns emerge—both in terms of algorithmic performance and the inherent characteristics of each cluster.

When considering the cluster sizes, C1 stands out as the smallest (248 measurements); however, it shows comparatively high RMSE values across the algorithms. Due to the LoS conditions, it has lower median path loss than the other clusters, although there is variability thanks to fewer observations as well as the likelihood of local scatterers or slight obstructions. While GB presents competitive results (5.8047 dB) on this specific cluster, it is outperformed by SVM, which has the lowest CV RMSE (4.927 dB), while the test RMSE has 5.197 dB. C1's higher dispersion underlines

FIGURE 9. Box plot of Path-loss values per cluster.

FIGURE 10. Box plot of Total distance per cluster.

FIGURE 11. Box plot of Intersected elements per cluster.

the variability under even LoS conditions due to small changes in the geometry or receiver position.

C2 encompasses the largest subset of measurements (1170 points) as well as low-obstruction conditions; both GB and kNN offer solid performance in this cluster. GB's CV RMSE is 2.626 dB while kNN's is 2.837 dB, with both

demonstrating low error levels in the test set. It seems that tree-based ensembles and instance-based methods are well-equipped to handle such moderate distances and partially obstructed paths, likely because the environment introduces attenuation patterns that are consistent yet relatively simple.

In C3 (610 measurements), the environment is generally obstructed more uniformly, producing path-loss values clustered between 93 and 98 dB. The model performance is overall excellent in this cluster, with GB achieving an especially low CV RMSE (1.683 dB) and test RMSE (1.9978 dB), with SVM coming close behind. The path-loss measurements present a tight spread, implying a stable diffraction or shadowing profile, allowing multiple algorithms to reliably fit the data more easily.

Lastly, C4 encompasses 462 points with longer distances and greater obstructions; nevertheless, GB once more shows the best performance, with a test RMSE of 1.7041 dB and the lowest MAPE (1.2%). Although kNN, SVM, and NN do less well in this cluster, the tree-ensemble methodology of GB appears especially suited to determining the greater variations in the distance and obstacle layouts. Contrastingly, NN has its highest errors in this cluster, implying that the network architecture or the training setup is less effective for this group’s severe distances and obstructions.

Overall, Gradient Boosting proves to be consistently robust across all clusters, suggesting it can adapt well to both LoS and low-obstructed scenarios (as in C1–C2) and more complex, highly obstructed conditions (C3–C4). Still, certain clusters show specific nuances (e.g., SVM’s strong performance in C1, kNN’s competitiveness in C2), hinting that specialized modeling might be advantageous in clusters with unique propagation characteristics. The imbalance in cluster sizes should also be noted, as it can influence error metrics and model confidence—yet the general conclusion remains that combining cluster-specific analysis with robust algorithms like GB can lead to more precise and reliable path-loss predictions.

The ranking of features by cluster—through the Permutation Feature Importance technique—allows us to characterize what influences most in each of the environments, taking into account the descriptions that have been made so far. It should be mentioned that, in C1, since it is equivalent to LoS, no feature importance can be given because it is a direct view, with no intersecting elements that give rise to the rest of the geospatial features. This way, the results for the ranking of features by cluster—considering, in each case, the algorithm which yielded a lowest MAPE in the test phase, that is, kNN in C2, and GB in both C3 and C4—are shown in Figures 13 to 15, as a function of the decrease in CVRMSE (Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Squared Error), for C2 to C4, respectively. As can be observed in Figure 13, the large decrease in CVRMSE shows that, among the features considered, the separation between transmitter and receiver (Total distance) is the principal driver of path loss in C2.

FIGURE 12. Box plot of each cluster’s final free distance.

FIGURE 13. Permutation-based feature importance for C2, considering kNN, identifying the key factors affecting path loss.

FIGURE 14. Permutation-based feature importance for C3, considering GB, identifying the key factors affecting path loss.

In fact, it aligns with standard propagation theory, wherein distance is the dominant factor influencing attenuation, particularly for moderate-range scenarios as is the case of C2. Regarding Figure 14, the Final free distance is the most influential factor for C3, since altering the distance from the last obstacle to the receiver in this kind of moderately to highly-obstructed scenarios significantly impairs model performance. Not in vain, a longer unobstructed path near the receiver generally lowers attenuation, but any variation in that segment (e.g., additional obstacles or reduced free space) can substantially alter the received signal level. Finally, Figure 15 shows how randomizing the Average free distance feature yields the largest drop in accuracy in C4, indicating it is the dominant predictor for such cluster. In this sense, since C4 involves more complex or extended paths, the aggregate length of unobstructed segments exerts a critical influence on path loss: longer mean free-space intervals tend to reduce overall attenuation, making this feature highly predictive.

FIGURE 15. Permutation-based feature importance for C4, considering GB, identifying the key factors affecting path loss.

TABLE 6. ML algorithm performance (RMSE dB, MAPE%, and R2) overall, for CV, train, and test sets.

Total (2490)	CV (RMSE, dB)	Train (RMSE, dB)	Test (RMSE, dB)	Test (MAPE, %)	Test (R ²)
GB	3.2580	2.9569	3.4446	3.10	0.943
kNN	3.1750	2.4158	3.1962	2.70	0.951
NN	3.7570	4.0166	4.0557	3.70	0.922
SVM	3.5390	3.3610	3.6090	3.17	0.938

When evaluating the models for path loss prediction on the entire dataset (2490 measurements, Table 6) without distinguishing clusters, the aggregated metrics still reflect the underlying influence of cluster size and composition.

Notably, C2 (which contains nearly half of the data points) may heavily sway the global results, given that its path-loss patterns are moderately complex yet not as extreme as those from the more distant or highly obstructed clusters. In this combined scenario, kNN achieves the lowest test RMSE (3.1962 dB), the smallest MAPE (2.7%), and the highest R², indicating that local, instance-based predictions can perform well when a large portion of the measurements belong to low-obstructed conditions.

GB, however, remains highly competitive (test RMSE of 3.4446 dB) and, importantly, shows consistent performance across varying conditions. The NN model appears to struggle somewhat, with both its training and test errors being higher, suggesting that in a dataset combining such diverse cluster characteristics, a single NN configuration might not capture the full range of propagation regimes without further tuning or an expanded architecture. SVM also does respectably, with a test RMSE of 3.6090 dB, but it does not outperform kNN or GB in this broad, unsegmented context. Overall, the results underscore how cluster imbalances—particularly a large subset dominated by moderate path loss—can shift global metrics in favor of algorithms that excel under mid-range or quasi-LoS scenarios.

Regarding the uncertainty budget of the presented results, our measurement pipeline was designed to minimize bias (GPS-disciplined timing; fixed Tx chain; calibrated 3 dBi monopole at the Rx; constant generator power with nearly constant EIRP). However, three main uncertainty sources remain: positioning error, power-measurement repeatability / small-scale fading, and equipment tolerances / absolute

offset. First, the “high-accuracy” GPS integrated with the analyzer typically yields meter-level horizontal error; propagating this to path-loss via a log-distance sensitivity distance shows that uncertainty contributes sub-dB except very close to the Tx. Moreover, with 1 s sampling while walking (~1 m spacing at 900 MHz, wavelength ~0.33 m), small-scale fading is only partially averaged; instrument repeatability and near-field dynamics typically add ~1–2 dB scatter. Finally, we did not perform a back-to-back calibration; any fixed chain loss/gain error thus appears as a global offset that affects the intercept but not the comparative RMSE/MAPE across models (all fit to the same labels). Therefore, taken together, we expect the irreducible label noise to be on the order of ~1–2 dB, which is consistent with the residual structure we observe: clustered GB models reach ~1.7–2.0 dB RMSE in obstructed regimes, approaching the measurement-noise floor, and ~3–4 dB on the aggregate set where heterogeneity dominates.

To contextualize our results, it should be mentioned that recent ML approaches in urban UHF commonly achieve RMSE ~ 3.5–10 dB on held-out data. For instance, Abolade et al. reported SVM RMSE ~ 10 dB on urban data at 900 MHz [11]. Iliev et al. evaluated an Artificial NN (ANN)-based compound model at 900 MHz, reporting RMSE ~ 7.3 dB on their urban dataset [37]. Abraham (Generalized Regression NN, 900 MHz, Jos City) reported RMSE ~ 4.28–4.52 dB [38]. Tikaria and Saxena Nigam proposed a kNN-based UHF predictor which attained RMSE ~ 3.5 dB and MAPE ~ 4% [39]. In this context, it should be noted that our geospatially conditioned models at 900 MHz yield RMSE = 3.196 dB on the entire dataset (kNN) and ~ 1.7–2.0 dB in obstructed clusters (GB), thus surpassing above mentioned accuracies while offering regime-specific interpretability via permutation feature importance. These comparisons reinforce our central claim: explicit conditioning on cadastral/DSM-derived descriptors is a simple, reproducible way to secure state-of-the-art accuracy in urban path-loss prediction without relying on expensive ray-tracing or image capture. Moreover, it is worth noting that, in urban path-loss prediction, it is widely considered an RMSE ≲ 2 dB as excellent (near the measurement/label-noise floor), 2–4 dB as good and suitable for planning, 4–6 dB as acceptable when only coarse inputs are available, and >6 dB as poor for site-specific decisions (though still serviceable for broad coverage studies). By these thresholds, our cluster-specific GB errors (~1.7–2.0 dB) are excellent, and our global kNN error (3.20 dB) is good—both notably below common fade-margin values and well below distance-only empirical baselines.

As an extra point of reference, we also benchmark, in Table 7, classical empirical models (Okumura-Hata, urban; COST231, medium city; ECC-33; and ITU-R P.1411-11, urban obstacles) on the entire dataset (without clustering).

As can be observed in Table 7, the traditional empirical models show substantially larger errors than the multivariate ML models in our study. Such gap is expected because

TABLE 7. Performance of classical empirical models (RMSE dB, MAPE%, and R2) overall.

Total (2490)	RMSE, dB	MAPE, %	R ²
Okumura-Hata	26.96	31.06	-2.466
COST-231	17.84	19.61	-0.518
ECC-33	46.81	55.09	-9.45
ITU	20.26	22.71	-0.958

FIGURE 16. Permutation-based feature importance overview (all clusters), for kNN algorithm, identifying the key factors affecting path loss.

FIGURE 17. Scatter plot of predicted (with the kNN algorithm) vs. measured path-loss (test set), illustrating model accuracy and biases.

empirical formulas do not encode the path-specific obstruction geometry that our geospatial descriptors capture.

In Figure 16, the permutation-based feature importance overview, considering all clusters at once and the kNN algorithm (the technique with the lowest MAPE in the test phase, as indicated in Table 6), is shown. As can be observed, the Total distance emerges as the most critical feature when assessing path loss across the entire dataset, followed by the Average free distance, both of which emphasize the significance of large-scale geometric separation and open-space segments. Meanwhile, the Final free distance and the Initial free distance remain relevant but contribute less to the overall predictive power within the aggregated context.

Finally, Figure 17 depicts a scatter plot comparing measured path-loss values (shown in red) against the predicted path-loss for the test set—via the algorithm with the lowest MAPE in the test phase, that is, kNN—, superimposed on a color scale (yellow-green-blue) indicating the magnitude of error (in dB). The horizontal axis represents the total distance from the transmitter, while the vertical axis indicates the path-loss level (in dB).

Visually, one can discern areas where the model’s predictions closely overlap with the measured data (green markers aligned with red ones), reflecting good accuracy and relatively small errors (blue to light green on the legend). However, there are also instances of noticeable deviation, where the predicted values depart from the measured points by several dB. These deviations are indicated by blue and yellow hues on the legend, signifying larger negative or positive errors, respectively. Overall, the figure reveals that the model’s performance remains robust across a substantial range of distances, but pockets of discrepancy emerge at certain intervals—often at larger distances or potentially where urban obstructions cause abrupt, localized increases in attenuation. Consequently, this scatter plot highlights both the strengths of the predictive model in capturing broad path-loss trends and the potential biases or underestimations that may arise under more complex propagation conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The feasibility of applying ML techniques for the analysis and prediction of radio wave propagation losses in urban environments has been explored through clustering methods, PCA, multivariate ML-based regression models and feature importance evaluation. To this end, a complete dataset comprising both a measurement campaign conducted at 900 MHz in Cartagena, Spain and a set of relevant geospatial variables—obtained through digital terrain and cadastral maps— has been considered.

The results obtained show how parameters such as the total distance between the transmitter (Tx) and the receiver (Rx), the number of intersected elements or the final free distance between the last obstacle and the Rx can be essential to differentiate the four clusters identified from the path loss measurements. In this sense, C1, representing LoS conditions, exhibited the lowest path loss, whereas C4, corresponding to highly obstructed conditions, had the highest attenuation, thereby demonstrating the importance of considering both distance and environmental morphology in path loss modeling. Concretely, beyond confirming the dominant role of Tx–Rx distance, our results identify regime-specific geometric mechanisms that remain predictive after controlling for distance. PCA indicates that distance governs the primary axis of variation (PC1 ~ 87.6%, with ~99% loading from Total distance), whereas the second axis (PC2 ~ 7.15%) is driven by Final free distance, highlighting the impact of the last unobstructed stretch near the receiver on the residual loss. Consistently, permutation-based importance reveals that in low-obstruction regimes (C2) distance is paramount, in moderately obstructed regimes (C3) the final free segment most shapes path loss, and in heavily obstructed regimes (C4) the granularity of interior clear gaps—captured by Average free distance—becomes the dominant predictor.

In addition, among all the algorithms analyzed, GB has proved to be consistently robust across all clusters when it comes to predicting propagation losses, suggesting that its ability to model complex, non-linear relationships makes

it particularly effective in both low- and highly obstructed environments. On the contrary, when evaluating the models for path loss prediction on the entire dataset (without distinguishing clusters), kNN has achieved the lowest test RMSE and the smallest MAPE, with the total distance Tx-Rx, the final free distance and the average free distance emerging as the most critical features for enhanced path-loss prediction. For its part, NN yielded the worst RMSE and MAPE test values, both when considering each cluster separately and for the entire dataset, indicating the need, in this case, for further optimization such as expanded training datasets.

The findings of this study can have significant implications for urban planners and network engineers, as they provide a framework for optimizing wireless network performance in complex urban environments. Thus, by integrating real-time data and adaptive strategies, the proposed models can respond to evolving urban conditions and user demands, ensuring resilient and efficient connectivity. Furthermore, the insights gained from this work can support investigation related to the application of ML in urban path loss prediction by considering the features that better contextualize the models with respect to the surrounding environment. Specifically, beyond our empirical results, our findings suggest a pragmatic recipe for researchers tackling urban path-loss with ML models. First, PCA can be treated as an exploratory tool to understand variance structure (e.g., distance vs. free-distance geometry), not as a mandatory feature transform for the final models. Furthermore, when geospatial descriptors are available and the environment is heterogeneous (mixed LoS/NLoS with varying obstruction severity), unsupervised clustering in the original feature space is beneficial: learning one model per regime delivers the largest accuracy gains—particularly in obstructed conditions—and enables regime-specific interpretability via permutation feature importance. In such clustered settings, a regularized tree ensemble (GB) proved the most robust and accurate across regimes. However, when clustering cannot be supported operationally, a global kNN (distance-weighted, with standardized inputs) is a strong, low-overhead baseline that matched or exceeded other families on the aggregate dataset.

Finally, in order to further enhance the accuracy and applicability of path loss prediction models, future research could explore several aspects such as dataset expansion through collecting measurements at different frequencies and across diverse urban landscapes, the exploration of deep learning approaches including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), or the consideration of classification-based analyses, where ML models classify areas into signal quality clusters rather than predicting continuous path loss values. Moreover, future work could be focused on augmenting our framework with conformal prediction (per-cluster) to deliver coverage-guaranteed prediction intervals, and/or quantile boosting to

obtain model-based intervals, thereby coupling accurate point predictions with calibrated uncertainty bands that expand in complex NLoS regimes and shrink in LoS-like conditions. This would let practitioners report both a point estimate and a calibrated uncertainty band, making our framework more actionable for radio-planning decisions.

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